

CHANG AND ITS ROLE IN UZBEK MUSIC

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Annotation: *This article describes the structure of the Uzbek folk instrument, its history, as well as practical instructions for teaching using pedagogical technologies.*

Key words: *music art, instrument performance, pedagogical technology, world music art, composer, method.*

It is known from history that the performance of songs and dances accompanied by musical instruments was widely used in public holidays and ceremonies of our people. By the middle of the 20th century, there was a growing interest in performing in groups and songs in groups. The process is widely used in the field of folklore and professional art. Folk music and dance ensembles of various compositions have become popular in the practice of performing folk music. Vocal ensembles, separate instrumental and vocal ensembles were formed and functioned in the development of culture. Vocal ensembles of different compositions (monophonic, polyphonic) are especially popular among young people.

Indeed, the performance practices of musicians around the world are based on the principles of constant growth, innovation, adaptation and development. The development of the practice of instrumental performance is adapted to the way in which musicians improve their skills, harmonize the cultures of different peoples, and perform large-scale events with small ensembles. It is important to popularize this style among young people. The development of solo performance skills has had a major impact on the development of team performance skills, as well as a better understanding and performance of the musical culture and art of the peoples of the world. In order to demonstrate this process in practice, the teachers of the conservatory took the initiative and came up with a specific proposal in order to continue the demonstration of the innumerable potential of Uzbek folk instruments.

The rich tradition of folk instruments has been reflected in the practice of performance. Fascinating people with beautiful voices has always been associated with fun moments in the practice of musicians. Demonstrating the power of each word in the performance of a particular instrument is the fruit of the beautiful combination of the instrument performer and the instrument. It means demonstrating the level of opportunity and skill based on experience. If this interpretation combines two, three, four or more instruments and they form a beautiful pair or ensemble, it will surely delight any listener. This is probably why in the practice of performing, the art of percussion, the discussion of instruments, their harmony and performance as an ensemble have always served a delicate taste and a beautiful relationship.

At the end of the summary, we can say that musical activity is an integral part of all our educational work, and its role in the harmonic development of young people is great. Therefore, at present, many creative communities are being established in our country in a large number of music schools, schools and extracurricular children, cultural whitening institutions, in the presence of production organizations. In this regard, the role of national music in the spiritual harmonious upbringing of young people is of particular importance.

Because the role of our national music is of particular importance for the young people of ayin, because the National Music Art also has a role in the preservation of the values inherent in our national mentality. It is known that the art of national music contributes to the further development of sincerity and mutual affection among young people. On the floor of the content and essence of musical education lies the perfect human upbringing of a harmonious generation. It is natural, of course, to put the question of what should be the social qualities of educators in the implementation of the process of continuous musical education. Pedagogical technology is the optimal organization of training processes. The choice of instructional materials, the change in form and size, adapted to the strength, mastering characteristics of the re-developed pupil or student, also affects educational technology. Pedagogical technology, in turn, is a system of development and improvement of educational processes, the content of education, methods and tools, based on the object of education and diagnostic purposes, that is, the educational process that embodies the innovations of Science and technology

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